

Book of Abstracts

BLUE GROWTH: CHALLENGES AND OPPORTUNITIES FOR THE BLACK SEA MARBLUE 2022

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- **Session I: Oceanography, Marine Geology and GeoEcology**
- **Session II: Biodiversity, Ecology and Conservation of Marine Ecosystems**
- **Session III: Sustainable Use of Marine Resources**
- **Session IV: Observing the Black Sea**
- **Session V: Marine Spatial Planning (MSP), Coastal Management and Ocean Literacy**
- **Special Session: European Marine Research Infrastructures: supporting Blue Growth in the Black Sea**

Editors:

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PARAMETERIZING THE IMPACT OF CLIMATE CHANGE ON SEDIMENT TRANSPORTATION TO THE FISHING PORTS OF TURKEY IN THE BLACK SEA

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Abstract. Terrigenous sedimentation has been accelerated by the unusually high rain that fell in the Eastern Black Sea during recent years as a result the escalated sedimentation negatively affects fishing ports located in the regions. The severe sedimentation at the port entry endangers navigational infrastructure and affects the port depth required for quick and secure fish unloading, ultimately affecting the blue growth in the region. In order to examine how climate change accelerates sedimentation in three important fishing ports, Yoroz-Trabzon, Trabzon, Fındıklı-Rize, and Hopa-Artvin, all of which are situated on Turkey's Eastern Black Sea coast, we have been conducting a series of field surveys. In this research, we look at innovative ways to prevent this serious problem while calibrating sediment movement at fishing ports in the Eastern Black Sea. The preliminary findings will be shared with a detailed discussion during the oral presentation.

Keywords: *Black Sea, blue growth, fishing ports*

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